

Effectiveness of selected natural disaster management training programme on knowledge among people residing in selected community areas

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ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION

A disaster is a significant disruption of a society's normal operations that results in significant losses of people, property, or the environment that are greater than what the impacted society can reasonably expect to recover from on its own. India is one of the most disaster-prone nations in the world; nearly 80% of India's land area is thought to be susceptible to at least one form of natural disaster. In India, disasters affected 65 million people annually from 2000 to 2009. on average, 3.25 million of whom were lactating and pregnant mother Disasters impact 8.45 million children under the age of five each year, and 1.25 million of them are malnourished.

OBJECTIVES: -

To assess the effectiveness of selected natural disaster management training programme on knowledge among people residing in selected community areas.

HYPOTHESIS

H0: There is no significant association between selected natural disaster management programme on knowledge among people residing in selected community areas. (p=0.05)

H1: There is significant association selected natural disaster management programme on knowledge among people residing in selected community areas. (p=0.05).

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Pre experimental one-group pre-test post-test research design, The research methodology adopted for the study employed a quantitative research approach. The investigator utilized a Pre experimental one-group pretest post-test research design, Accessible population is an urban community people of selected areas. 60 samples were taken by non-probability convenient sampling techniques. A single group comprising 60 samples was selected using a non-

probability convenient sampling technique. The sample was chosen based on specific inclusion criteria from the selected community. The research tool comprised demographic data and a structured questionnaire designed to assess the effectiveness of selected natural disaster management training programme on knowledge among people residing in selected community areas.

RESULT: -

This study shows that,31.7% of the community people had age 20- 25 years, 56.7% of them were age 26-30 years, 8.3% of them were age 30-35 years and 3.3% of them were age 35 years and above.36.7% of them were males, 61.7% of them were females and 1.7% of them had another gender. 40% of them had a family income of Rs. 10000-15000, 53.3% of them had family income of Rs. 20000- 30000 and 5% of them had family income of Rs. 30000-40000 and 1.7% of their family income of Rs. 40000-50000.83.3% of them had attended Training/ Workshop regarding Disaster Management and 16.7% of them did not attend Training/ Workshops regarding Disaster Management.5% of them had information regarding disaster management from mass media, 20% of them had information from mass media, first aider, 10% of them had information from mass media, first aider, websites, 18.3rd had information from mass media, websites, 1.7% of them had information from mass media, health personnel and websites, 18.3% of them had information from mass media, websites, 20% of them had information from mass media, first aider, health personnel, 1.7% of them had information from first aider, health personnel, web sites and 5% of them had information from first aider and websites.

KEY POINTS

Effectiveness, natural, disaster, training ,programme, knowledge, community.

INTRODUCTION

“A disaster is a significant disruption of a society's normal operations that results in significant losses of people, property, or the environment that are greater than what the impacted society can reasonably expect to recover from on its own. India is one of the most disaster-prone nations in the world; nearly 80% of India's land area is thought to be susceptible to at least one form of natural disaster. In India, disasters affected 65 million people annually from 2000 to 2009. on average, 3.25 million of whom were lactating and pregnant mother Disasters impact 8.45 million children under the age of five each year, and 1.25 million of them are malnourished. The majority of INDIA is heavily impacted by both floods and droughts, though they are most common in the country's northwest and east, respectively THE HIMALAYAN area in the north and northeast of the nation is impacted by geophysical hazards, which rank in the high declines for mortality and the low declines for GDP effect. Cyclones have a high mortality rate but only affect a small portion of the nation. At least one hazard has a significant impact on this multi-hazard mortality of the total nation, and mortality impacts are especially concentrated in the north and northeastern regions. Since the tsunami in the INDIAN OCEAN in 2004, INDIA has also become significantly more susceptible to tsunamis. Nearly 57% of the area is at risk from earthquakes (high seismic zones III-V), 68% from drought, 8% from cyclones, and 12% from flooding².

BACKGROUND OF STUDY

A natural catastrophe happens when a community is severely impacted by a natural event and the damage is so severe that outside assistance is required. Such instances are the recent tragic catastrophes in Haiti, Chile and Pakistan in 2010, Queensland 2010 - 2011, Christchurch and Japan in 2011, which collectively accounted for 333,944 casualties and economic damages estimated at between 199 and 327 billion US dollars (Erskine and Gregg, 2012). Using reactive actions to stop these incidents from becoming catastrophes is one strategy to lessen the effects of this devastation Bahraini et al., 2009; Poser and Drench, 2010). Hence, a strategy must be used to increase communities' resilience and give them the ability to withstand, adapt, or transform when a crisis strikes Mediondo, 2010; Norris et al., 2008).). Disaster management is an alternative to improving resilience and thus avoids or reduces the impact of natural disasters (Bahrain et al., 2009).

NEED OF THE STUDY

In 2023, there were 330 natural disaster events. Asia experienced the highest number of natural disasters, most likely due to its size and susceptibility.⁸ Developing countries suffer the greatest costs when a disaster hits-more than 95% of all deaths caused by hazards occur in developing countries, and loss due to natural hazards are 20 times greater (as a percentage of GDP) in developing countries than in industrialized countries¹⁶. (Bahrain et al., 2009) Examining the conventional disaster management cycle, highlighting the value of introducing modern management ideas into the cycle, and suggesting a conceptual model that embodies modern management understanding of the cycle are the main objectives of this study. The literature shows that people all around the world, as well as academics, still significantly rely on the traditional disaster management life-cycle to manage catastrophes and big incidents. This consists of four basic stages: preparedness, mitigation, response, and recovery. The study of catastrophe and emergency management still lacks contemporary management ideas and knowledge.

PRIMARY OBJECTIVES: -

To assess the effectiveness of selected natural disaster management training programme on knowledge among people residing in selected community areas.

SECONDARY OBJECTIVES:

1. To assess the knowledge of the people residing in selected community areas.
2. To assess the effectiveness of selected natural disaster training programme on knowledge among people residing in selected community areas.
3. To compare the association between pre-test score with selected demographic variables.

HYPOTHESIS

H₀: There is no significant association between selected natural disaster management programme on knowledge among people residing in selected community areas. (p=0.05)

H₁: There is significant association selected natural disaster management programme on knowledge among people residing in selected community areas. (p=0.05).

METHODOLOGY

A research methodology defines what the activity of research is, how to proceed, how to measure progress and what constitutes success. Methodology is a significant part of any study, enabling the researcher to project the research undertaken. Research methodology is the systematic way to carry out an academic study and research in a flawless manner. The methodology enables the researcher to project a blueprint of the details, data, approach, analysis, findings of research undertaken. The research approach is a systematic, objective method of discovery with empirical evidence and rigorous experimental. The research approach was used because the present study aimed at evaluating the effectiveness of selected natural disaster management training programmed on knowledge among people residing in selected community areas. This study is aimed at developing, determining and evaluating the effectiveness of selected natural disaster management training programmed on knowledge among people residing in a selected community. The research approach adopted in this study is **Quantitative Approach. Pre-experimental one group pre-test post-test research design, The sample size, n comes to be 58 which is to consider 60 samples.** The research approach refers to the investigator's overall plan for obtaining answers to the research questions and for testing the research hypothesis. It spells out the strategies that the investigator adopts to develop information that is accurate, objective and interpreted.

SECTION- I

This table shows that, 31.7% of the community people had age 20- 25 years, 56.7% of them had age 26-30 years, 8.3% of them had age 30-35 years and 3.3% of them were age 35 years and above. 36.7% of them were males, 61.7% of them were females and 1.7% of them had another gender. 40% of them had a family income of Rs. 10000-15000, 53.3% of them had family income of Rs. 20000- 30000 and 5% of them had family income of Rs. 30000-40000 and 1.7% of them had a family income of Rs. 40000-50000. 83.3% of them had attended Training/ Workshop regarding Disaster Management and 16.7% of them did not attend Training/ Workshops regarding Disaster Management. 5% of them had information regarding disaster management from mass media, 20% of them had information from mass media, first aider, 10% of them had information from mass media, first aider, websites, 18.3% of them had information from mass media, websites, 1.7% of them had information from mass media, health personnel and websites, 18.3% of them had information from mass media, websites, 20% of them had information from mass media, first aider, health personnel, 1.7% of them had information from first aider, health personnel, web sites and 5% of them had information from first aider and websites

SECTION II

Analysis of data related to knowledge of the people residing in selected community areas.

SECTION III

Analysis of data related to the effectiveness of selected natural disaster training program on knowledge among people residing in selected community areas.

In pretest, 85% of the community people had poor knowledge (score 0-8) and 15% of them had average knowledge (score 9-16) regarding natural disaster management. In post-test, 8.3% of them had poor knowledge (score 0-8), 55% of them had average knowledge (score 9-16) and 36.7% of them had good knowledge (score 17-25) regarding natural disaster management. This indicates that the knowledge among community people regarding natural disaster management improved remarkably after training program.

Paired t-test for the effectiveness of selected natural disaster training program on knowledge among people residing in selected community areas.

ITEM ANALYSIS

SECTION IV

Analysis of data related to the association between knowledge among community people regarding natural disaster management with selected demographic variables.

Since all the p-values were large (greater than 0.05), none of the demographic variables was found to have significant association with the knowledge among community people regarding natural disaster management.

DISCUSSION

The present study is Quantitative Research, Pre-experimental one group pre-test and post-test design in this study which has adopted a Quantitative approach to assessing. Effectiveness of selected natural disaster management training programme on knowledge among people residing in selected community areas. The study objectives in the data gathered were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics to reach meaningful conclusions.

LIMITATION

1. The study was limited to old age people.
2. This study is limited to knowledge and attitude regarding disaster in the community area.
3. The tool used was not standardized
4. The study was conducted using non- probability purposive sampling technique.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The researcher recommends the following studies.
 2. The study can be done in a large sample size to confirm the results of the study. The descriptive study can be conducted to assess the effectiveness of selected natural disaster management training programme on knowledge among people residing in selected community areas.
 3. An evaluative study can be done to determine the effectiveness of a planned health training programme
1. A similar can be undertaken by using different teaching methods.
 2. Study finding can be useful for the administrative level.
 3. The comparative study can be conducted.

CONCLUSION

This chapter presents the conclusion drawn, implications, limitations and recommendations. Effectiveness of selected natural disaster management training programme on knowledge among people residing in selected community areas.

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